

CHARACTERIZATION OF INTERLAMINAR FRACTURE TOUGHNESS OF CFRP LAMINATES TOUGHENED BY CNT-DISPERSED RESIN INTERLAYERS

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Keywords: *Interlaminar fracture toughness, Carbon nanotube, Interlayer*

1 Introduction

Carbon Fiber Reinforced Plastics (CFRP) have been used in various fields, especially in the field of aeronautics and astronautics for reducing structural weight because they have high specific strength and specific stiffness. However, owing to the poor mechanical properties in through-the-thickness direction, CFRP laminates are generally susceptible to delamination accumulation when the laminates are subject to impacts from out-of-plane directions. This limits the dramatic application of CFRP laminates in aircraft structures.

Nanofibers and nano-particles have been expected as superior reinforcements of CFRP laminates. In particular, carbon nanotubes (CNTs) possess exceptional mechanical properties. The incorporation of CNTs into the polymers is expected to contribute to the improvement of the mechanical properties of three-phase nanocomposites consisting of traditional long fibers and CNT-dispersed polymers[1-3]. Our previous study indicated that unidirectional CFRP laminates with CNT-dispersed matrix have higher mode-I and mode-II interlaminar fracture toughness compared to traditional CFRP laminates[4].

In addition, one of the promising ways to increase the interlaminar properties of CFRP laminates is to place the resin layer between the prepregs. This is often called as “interleaf” or “interlayer” method. Mode-I and mode-II interlaminar fracture properties of carbon/epoxy laminates with the self-same epoxy interlayer are higher than those of traditional CFRP laminates under both static and fatigue loadings[5].

The main purpose of this research is to improve interlaminar fracture toughness of CFRP laminates using CNT-dispersed resin interlayers with minimal loss of in-plane mechanical properties of the laminates. Unidirectional CFRP laminates with

CNT-dispersed interlayers are prepared for the characterization of interlaminar fracture toughness. Comparative studies of the measured interlaminar fracture toughness between CFRP with and without CNT-dispersed interlayers are provided.

2 Experiment

2.1 Experimental Procedure

Unidirectional prepregs were prepared by Arisawa Manufacturing Co., Ltd. using T700SC-12K fibers and epoxy (EP827) filled with cup-stacked carbon nanotubes (2wt%). The cup-stacked carbon nanotubes used in this study were CARBERE[®] (supplied by GSI Creos Corporation). The prepreg fiber areal weight was set to be 125 g/m², and the nominal resin content including CNTs was 33 wt%. CNT-dispersed epoxy films were also prepared as interlayers in order to investigate the effect of CNT-dispersed interlayers on interlaminar fracture toughness of CFRP laminates. Four types of specimens were fabricated as follows.

- A: [0]₂₄ laminates without interlayers
- B: [0]₂₄ laminates with an epoxy interlayer without CNTs
- C: [0]₂₄ laminates with a CNT(AR10, 2.4wt%)-dispersed interlayer
- D: [0]₂₄ laminates with a CNT(AR23, 2.4wt%)-dispersed interlayer

Unidirectional laminates were stacked and fabricated at 130°C using a hot press. Interlayers were placed during the layup process only at the middle surface, where the crack propagates during the tests in this study. In order to induce the initial cracks between the middle layers, thin release films were partially placed adjacent to the middle layer or the interlayers during fabrication. Prior to the tests, pre-cracks were

carefully introduced in order to avoid blunt crack tips.

In order to obtain mode-I and mode-II interlaminar fracture toughness, double cantilever beam (DCB) tests and end-notched flexure (ENF) tests are performed at room temperature using the prepared specimens. According to the test standard (JIS K 7086), specimens with 150 mm length and 25 mm width were used for DCB tests and specimens with 140 mm length and 25 mm width were used for ENF tests. Five specimens were used for each test. The cross section of specimen C is shown in Fig. 1. The interlayer film, the thin release film, and the simulated initial crack are identified.

2.2 Results and discussion

2.2.1 DCB tests

Fig. 2-5 indicate the relation between the mode-I interlaminar fracture toughness and the crack length (R-curve) of each specimens (A-D). In general, fracture toughness increases as the crack propagates because of the “fiber bridging”. According to the figures, some specimens exhibit higher initial mode-I interlaminar fracture toughness compared to others. In these cases, fiber bridging is considered to occur even at the initial stage of crack propagation, as the initial fracture toughness is comparable to the fracture toughness when the crack extended. The fiber bridging observed at the initial stage of crack propagation can be shown in Fig. 6, which is the micrograph of the fracture surface of one of these specimens. We can see the evidence of fiber bridging.

Fig. 7 and 8 show the initial and the propagation values of the mode-I interlaminar fracture toughness, respectively. Note that initial values are taken as the initial fracture toughness of specimens which exhibited no fiber bridging at the initial stage. According to JIS K 7086, the propagation value is calculated as the average of the values when the increment of crack length is between 20 mm and 60 mm. In Fig.7, the mean values of two specimens are shown for specimen A and D, and minimum values are shown for specimen B and C. In the Fig.8 the average data as well as the upper and lower limit are shown. Specimens B, C and D with interlayers have higher initial and propagation values of the mode-I interlaminar fracture toughness than specimens A without interlayers. In Fig.7, the initial value of specimen B is higher than that of specimen C. This

reason is related to the fiber bridging. Actually, the specimen which exhibited the minimum initial value among B-type specimens has the evidence of the fiber bridging slightly. Because of the fiber bridging, it is difficult to compare the initial data simply. However, it can be concluded that interlayers and CNTs in interlayers have something positive on the mode-I interlaminar fracture toughness of CFRP laminates.

2.2.2 ENF tests

The obtained mode-II interlaminar fracture toughness is shown in Fig. 9. In this research, ENF tests were conducted measuring the displacement at the central loading point, not the crack opening displacement. Therefore only the initial values of the mode-II interlaminar fracture toughness can be measured. The average data as well as the upper and the lower limit of the results are shown in the figure. Specimens B, C and D with interlayers have higher interlaminar fracture toughness than specimens A without interlayers. Furthermore, it can be seen that existence of CNTs in the interlayers has a positive effect on the improvement of mode-II fracture toughness, and the laminates including interlayers with higher aspect ratio (AR23) show higher fracture toughness than those including interlayers with lower aspect ratio (AR10).

3 Discussions and Conclusions

In this paper, CNT-dispersed interlayers were placed between the prepreg layers in order to improve interlaminar fracture toughness of CFRP laminates. Based on DCB tests the following results were obtained:

- Inserting interlayers can improve both of the initial and propagation values of mode-I interlaminar fracture toughness of CFRP laminates.
- CNTs in interlayers have positive effects on mode-I interlaminar fracture toughness of CFRP laminates.

In these tests, the evidence of the fiber bridging as shown in Fig.6 can be observed. However, the fiber bridging can't be evaluated quantitatively herein, and the number of the specimens used for comparison in this study may not be enough.

ENF tests indicated that:

- Resin interlayers and CNTs in interlayers can enhance Mode-II interlaminar fracture toughness of CFRP laminates.
- Mode-II interlaminar fracture toughness of laminates with longer CNTs (AR23) in interlayers is higher than that of laminates with shorter CNTs (AR10) in interlayers.

Results of DCB and ENF tests indicate that the presence of interlayers improve mode-I and mode-II interlaminar fracture toughness. This is because the resin-rich layer generated by inserting interlayers results in the enlargement of the damage zone, where the resin deforms elastically and plastically. This increases the energy consumption used in deformation of the resin, which may enhance the interlaminar fracture toughness. Fig. 10 and 11 are, respectively, the micrographs of fracture surface of specimen A (without interlayer) and C (with interlayer). In Fig. 11, the evidence of deformed resin can be observed, and this fracture surface is clearly different from that in Fig. 10. Additionally, CNTs in interlayers have positive effects on mode-I and mode-II interlaminar fracture toughness. One of the possible explanations is that the incorporation of CNTs into the interlayers increases the fracture surface due to crack deflection. Although mode-I interlaminar fracture toughness of specimens B without CNTs in interlayers is higher than that of specimens C with CNTs in interlayers, this can be related to the fiber bridging. The effect of fiber bridging is considered to be superior to that of increase of fracture surface because of CNTs. It is also concluded that longer CNTs (AR23) in interlayers are more effective than shorter CNTs (AR10) for the improvement of interlaminar fracture toughness.

This study suggested that interlayers and CNTs in interlayers improve the interlaminar fracture toughness of CFRP laminates, which makes us expect that CNT-dispersed interlayer can reduce the delamination accumulation. Now numerical and experimental studies are being performed in order to get knowledge on the optimized method of interlayer placement (e.g. numbers and locations of the interlayers between the prepregs) under the simulated loading conditions (e.g. out-of-plane loading) for efficient improvement of damage resistance of CFRP laminates by using CNT-dispersed interlayers.

Fig. 1. Cross sectional image of the specimen C

Fig. 2. R-curve of specimen A

Fig. 3. R-curve of specimen B

Fig. 4. R-curve of specimen C

Fig. 5. R-curve of specimen D

Fig. 6. Micrograph of fracture surface at the area of $\Delta a=0$ (at 5-fold magnification, specimen A)

Fig. 7. Comparison of initial values of mode-I interlaminar fracture toughness

Fig. 8. Comparison of propagation values of mode-I interlaminar fracture toughness

Fig. 9. Comparison of mode-II interlaminar fracture toughness

Fig. 10. Micrograph of fracture surface (at 50-fold magnification, specimen A)

Fig. 11. Micrograph of fracture surface (at 50-fold magnification, specimen C)

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